

**FAMILY SERVICES TO ETHNOCULTURAL GROUPS
IN METRO TORONTO**

United Way

A DISCUSSION PAPER

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Toronto is one of the most multiculturally diverse cities in the world, according to the World Health Organization. Over a third of the people living in Toronto were born outside Canada (UWGT, 1990:32). Less than half the city's population is Anglo-Saxon in origin (UWGT, 1990:30); and fewer than half have English as their mother tongue (WHO, 1990). Only about 43% of recent immigrants to Canada can speak either English or French at all (After the Door has been Opened, 1988:23).

Immigration will continue to be an important source of population growth for Ontario and Metro. By 1992, Canada will be accepting 250,000 immigrants a year, "to offset current population trends and to keep the economy healthy" (Toronto Star, Oct. 29, 1990). Metro will be home to about one-third. In previous decades, most immigrants came from Europe. More recent immigrants are often of Asian, Black or Latin American backgrounds -- visible minorities constitute 17.3% of Metro's population -- and many come from cultures which may find western assumptions about families (and therefore treatment approaches) inconsistent with their own values.

Toronto is one of the most multiculturally diverse cities in the world

In 1982, United Way of Greater Toronto (UWGT) reported a "pressing and critical need for further family services to ethnocultural and native communities in Metropolitan Toronto" (Task Force on Services to Ethnic and Native Communities). In the past eight years very little has changed. Mainstream family counselling organizations, by and large, are still unable to respond to the linguistic and cultural needs of many immigrant and ethnocultural communities.

Ethnocultural agencies continue to provide settlement and integration services without stable funding and without access to family counselling dollars. Though United Way has changed its own funding structures and priorities over the past few years - expanding its membership to include many new ethnocultural agencies - it has not had a significant impact on the lack of family services for ethnocultural groups.

Over a third of the people living in Toronto were born outside Canada

SUMMARY

A review of the research literature on family services to ethnocultural groups was carried out, along with interviews with over 20 individuals and groups. Some clear directions and themes emerged.

Intensifying financial pressure on all levels of government is leading to increased scrutiny of efficiency and cost effectiveness in models of service provision. It is important to avoid redundancies and parallel services whenever possible. However, most ethnocultural agencies are not parallel services. They are decentralized,

community-based services with flexibility in their methods of provision. Many of these agencies have proven credibility and established links within the communities they serve. Ethnocultural agencies are already an essential part of the service system but because their counselling and mental health services are informal and underfunded, these services are neither recognized nor valued. If funding continues to decrease to the point where these agencies are unable to provide the informal supports they have so far provided, the impact on our social system would be profound.

We recommend that a Community Services Act be introduced, defining essential community and family supports to be provided in municipalities across Ontario, along with their respective funding responsibilities. This Act should be consistent with legislation and policies in other key Ministries (particularly the upcoming Community Mental Health Act), and should ensure accessibility of family services to new Canadians. Some of the necessary supports are stable funding to many ethnocultural agencies, including those which provide settlement functions as well as counselling and mental health treatment; better co-ordination between the Ministries of Community & Social Services, Health and Citizenship regarding the 'grey area' between family services, settlement needs and mental health problems; multicultural organizational change to many 'mainstream' agencies which are currently unable to serve a multicultural clientele; and ongoing evaluation of approaches that result in real improvement with individuals and families.

Most ethno-cultural agencies are not parallel services

Short term approaches include a jointly funded pilot project to develop and assess appropriate family interventions (see Appendix C); the provision of trained interpreters in service areas which are not linguistically accessible to many new Canadians; and the development and support of new agencies and programs serving ethnocultural groups, where they are presently underserved.

Several different models of service delivery are necessary

Generally, United Way supports the recommendations of the Multicultural Coalition for Access to Family Services (see Appendix D), and specifically their emphasis on the necessity of using several different models of service delivery to respond to the needs of ethnocultural communities.

OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

The present study was initiated as a follow up to the 1982 Task Force report. There were two objectives: to provide directions to UWGT's government relations activities over the next few years in regard to family services, and to provide input to priority-setting for UWGT's distribution of funds, including member agencies, admissions and short term grants. It was also hoped that the recommendations of this report will be

useful to Metro Community Services in their current review of Ethnocultural Family Services.

Data collection consisted of a literature search on family and mental health problems among immigrants and ethnocultural groups, as well as twenty interviews with key informants. These informants included representatives from ethnocultural agencies, family counselling agencies and government departments and ministries from the federal, provincial and Metro levels. A list of the persons who were contacted is appended.

FOCUS AND DEFINITIONS

Partly as a result of preliminary data gathering, it was decided that the report would focus on ethnocultural communities which have immigrated to Canada in the past two generations, either voluntarily or as refugees. Even native-born Canadians may have difficulties benefitting from family counselling which does not acknowledge the values of immigrant parents or grandparents. Most of the following discussion will focus on people who were born in another country, since they present the most difficult problems in access to family services, but many points relating to cultural appropriateness will affect second or even third generation immigrants as well.

The report focuses on ethnocultural communities which have immigrated to Canada in the past two generations

Most ethnocultural agencies in Toronto provide at least some supports to immigrants adapting to their new country. Activities such as recreational, cultural, self-help and counselling often assist with the adaptation and settlement phases of their members even if settlement is not part of the official mandate. This review will refer to both settlement agencies and ethnocultural agencies -- although they are not always the same, they have many issues in common, both in the functions they play in the Metro service system, and in their chronic insecurity regarding funding.

'Mainstream services', in this report, refer to agencies or institutions which are funded by government to provide counselling or mental health services within a given geographic catchment area, regardless of their clients' ethnocultural background or language. Some mainstream services have developed resources in treating particular ethnocultural groups, such as the Catholic Immigration Bureau, Catholic Family Services of Toronto, Woodgreen Red Door Newcomer Project and Family Services Association of Metro Toronto. Generally, though, "studies by the Social Planning Council of Metro Toronto, the Children's Aid Society of Metro Toronto, and the Ministry of Community

"While mainstream agencies profess to be open to all, they are, in fact, highly inaccessible"

and Social Services illustrate the theme that while [mainstream] agencies profess to be open to all, they are, in fact, highly inaccessible" (Yelaja,1990:19).

Native peoples in Toronto have also been underserved and inappropriately served by generic counselling services. However, a separate review is recommended for Native communities, whose family counselling needs must be understood in a very different historical and funding context.

Finally, many factors make up the economic and social environment which so profoundly affects individual and family well-being. This paper addresses the role and delivery of family services in the context of a diverse ethnocultural population. Other issues, such as the impact of individual personality and the effectiveness of specific methods of intervention, are beyond the purview of this paper.

FACTORS AFFECTING MENTAL HEALTH OF IMMIGRANTS

Several factors associated with migration increase the risk for family and mental health problems, according to a comprehensive literature review ("Review of the Literature on Migrant Mental Health",1986:p.x). These factors include:

1. Drop in personal and socioeconomic status following migration;
2. Inability to speak the language of the host country;
3. Separation from family;
4. Lack of friendly reception by surrounding host population;
5. Isolation from persons of similar cultural background;
6. Traumatic experience or prolonged stress prior to migration; and
7. Adolescent or senior age at time of migration.

This paper addresses the role and delivery of family services in the context of a diverse ethnocultural population

Individuals affected by some or all of these variables appear to be at greatest risk for mental disorders between 3-18 months of arrival. This is long before a non-English speaker can gain enough fluency in English to benefit from counselling. A second period of high risk occurs several years after arrival, when immediate adaptation needs have been met.

Measures which prevent or reduce the impact of the above seven factors are essential in preventing family and mental health problems. Thus, a great deal of settlement and social support work has a direct effect on the mental health and adaptation of immigrant families. Assistance in finding a job, a friendly orientation and linking to the host society, an

Settlement in a thriving close-knit community provides an important support in enhancing the individuals' mental health

opportunity to socialize with people of the same background, all reduce the risk of having serious emotional and family problems. Settlement in a thriving, close-knit community provides an important support in enhancing the individual's mental health. Without a strong community of the same cultural background, immigrants seem to experience high levels of distress, including depression and family problems, at a rate of two to three times higher than other immigrants living in such a community (Beiser, 1989).

SETTLEMENT AGENCIES AND FAMILY SERVICES

Ethnocultural settlement agencies provide a link to the immigrant's ethnic community, as well as to the institutions of the host society. To many immigrants, these agencies comprise their community (Allmen, 1990). The agencies are responsible for linking the immigrants to their own community as well as to the community at large. They may even take the place of the extended family until other links are developed. Settlement counsellors are called upon to provide a wide variety of roles. As generalists, they come into first contact with all aspects of an immigrant's needs: employment, housing, social, health and family adaptation. When there are service gaps to immigrants, the settlement counsellors feel the impact, and often attempt to meet their clients' needs without adequate specialized skills or resources. Settlement agencies have repeatedly noted that they are unable to provide or refer clients to adequate family/mental health services given the current lack of supports and training. Immigrant communities, therefore, lack access to mandated psychiatric and mental health services.

Several factors associated with migration increase the risk for family and mental health problems

Ethnocultural agencies play a vital role in the areas of family counselling and mental health. The settlement worker at an agency is readily accepted as a credible and trusted helper. He or she is perceived in a dual role: 'belonging' to the immigrant's culture and to the host culture. The settlement worker not only acts as a role model for the immigrant's integration into the new community, but also provides the only gateway to mainstream community services. The ethnocultural agency, then, is in a position to do direct outreach with its clients with regard to mental health services. This outreach can happen in several ways: for example, teaching the immigrant family about Canadian laws against family violence, linking families to appropriate services, and consulting to mainstream services about the sociocultural backgrounds of their clients.

Ethnocultural agencies play a vital role in the areas of family counselling and mental health

Many immigrants, especially from countries which have no history of settlement in Canada, have neither established agencies which can help them in their own languages, nor a mature community to make them welcome. These newcomers

often attempt to join a fragmented and isolated community of other new arrivals, frequently without the organizational skills to set up networks in their new country. Individuals and families in crisis may benefit from interpreters to access generic counselling services, but the community needs its own network of supports to prevent family and mental health problems. Community development is often necessary for groups who wish to set up formal and informal networks but do not have the skills or knowledge to make them work in an unfamiliar culture.

MAINSTREAM AGENCIES AND FAMILY SERVICES

Services which are mandated to serve everyone within a geographic catchment area (the definition of mainstream) will of necessity be responsible to a large population of different ethnocultural groups. There are few areas of Metro Toronto which are characterized by ethnocultural uniformity. Mainstream services, then, by the fact of existing in a highly diverse metropolitan area, must be equipped to serve an ethnically diverse population. Yet most of these services are appropriate mainly to a Western, English-speaking clientele.

There are several barriers to counselling services provided by mainstream agencies. Since counselling and therapy by their nature are dependent upon communication, non-English speakers are unable to use counselling services without interpreters or counsellors who can speak their language. These two provisions are generally unavailable. It is important to note that, in crises, second language fluency is reduced significantly. A person's ability to communicate in English at her work may not predict her ability to understand counselling when under intense personal stress. Second, the stigmatization of mental health issues among immigrant communities may also deter individuals from going to a service 'or sick families'. Third, the fragmentation of service in our system is often bewildering to clients (not only immigrants!). To go to one agency for information about local resources, another for assistance in finding a job, and yet another to discuss family problems can be anxiety provoking at best, especially if they do not speak English fluently. For refugees, in particular, who may come from backgrounds in which government-supported social services can be instruments of suppression or even torture, each new contact with a strange institution can be frightening. Settlement counsellors may be the only social service providers that they can trust or communicate easily with. Finally, individuals who are raised within traditional families and cultures may be unaccustomed to talking about their feelings and acutely uncomfortable with the cultural assumptions inherent in Western counselling approaches. For example, many cultures do not distinguish between mental and physical disorders, and prefer to go to generalist healers. There

Immigrant communities lack access to mandated psychiatric and mental health services

In crisis, second language fluency is reduced significantly

is evidence that therapy is more effective when delivered by someone of the same cultural background as the client (Sue, 1990).

It will be many years before Toronto has a health and service system fully accessible by all of its residents. In the meantime, mainstream services have the function of providing specialized expertise that may be applied to particular groups through a variety of means. In the ideal case, each mainstream service develops resources (e.g., counsellors, consultants) that can relate to major ethnocultural groups in their areas. In other cases, the service makes links with ethnocultural agencies which can act as consultants and advocates for their clients. Some mainstream services are presently using these approaches.

Although many mainstream services acknowledge their deficiencies in relating to different ethnocultural groups, they also are in a financial squeeze. It is not likely that an institution already overburdened with clients will undertake an outreach program that will encourage still more people to approach them. For example, there are few funds for interpreters or consultants who can help them serve immigrants adequately. And often their staffing is stretched too thinly to experiment with different models of service delivery. Even using an interpreter, which seems rather straightforward, requires cultural sensitivity by the counsellor and generally more time to ensure that communication is clear and accurate for all participants.

Mainstream services, by the fact of existing in a highly diverse metropolitan area, must be equipped to serve an ethnically diverse population

Furthermore, professional clinical models of service are not always appropriate. Sometimes informal supports are more effective, because of the nature of the family problem, as a preventive measure, or because of the rather rigid roles prescribed by professional counselling. Not many mental health workers will assist families to fill out government forms, for example.

Mainstream agencies can assist settlement workers with the mental health aspects of their generalist counselling (e.g., when a worker discovers wife abuse while explaining where to learn English As a Second Language). Mental health workers can be assigned to provide consistent clinical supervision and training to settlement agency staff, for example. Mainstream agencies must have the staffing and funding to fill this role, but must be directly responsible to the communities they are attempting to serve. Too often service providers are not evaluated by the consumers of their services, and without close links with the communities, services will continue to be inappropriate.

Therapy seems to be more effective when delivered by someone of the same cultural background

FUNCTIONS OF ETHNOCULTURAL AGENCIES

In discussions of culturally appropriate family services, the argument is often presented that there cannot be a 'parallel' service system for each major ethnocultural community in Metro Toronto. A 'parallel' service system, including for example separate substance abuse treatment centres, separate in-patient psychiatric wards and separate child welfare systems, would be inefficient and expensive. However, the Provincial Government is increasingly moving towards community-based services, recognizing that services must respond to the needs and characteristics of specific communities in order to be maximally effective. A comprehensive service system should consist of three components: (a) local community-based agencies (see Appendix A) which are easy to approach and use by their client group. Programs and structures of accountability are tailored to the communities they serve (e.g., neighbourhood or ethnocultural group). These agencies are linked, through formal and informal networks, to (b) specialist services, which have expertise in areas of family service or mental health, and which are aimed at no single group in Metro. These two types of services may be large or small, centralized or decentralized, and are supported by (c) centralized resources which provide linking functions (like a Metro-wide Community Information Centre) or highly specialized 'tertiary' care (such as the provincial psychiatric hospitals).

Too often, service providers are not evaluated by the consumers of their services

In this system, ethnocultural agencies are not parallel services. They are decentralized, community-based services with flexibility in their methods of provision. The corporate plan of the Ministry of Community and Social Services (MCSS) and the directions of the Ministry of Health are entirely consistent with the locally-based delivery of services by agencies (see below, in section on Government Directions). Many of these agencies have proven credibility and established links within the communities they serve. Ethnocultural agencies are already an essential part of the service system but because their counselling and mental health services are often delivered by 'non-professionals', partly due to their lack of adequate funding, these services are neither recognized nor valued. If funding continues to decrease to the point where these agencies are unable to provide the informal supports they have so far provided, the impact on our social system would be profound.

The Provincial Government is increasingly moving towards community-based services

A recent paper on counselling and settlement in Ontario states: "The current service delivery system is locked into a mode of service that recognizes the existence of informal community-based ethnic services but does not recognize them as equal in service delivery and, therefore, uses them

Ethnocultural agencies are decentralized, community-based services

inappropriately, if at all. Equally, the informal ethnic-based service has given up trying to refer people to mainstream services because it only results in the client coming back bounced by the mainstream system" (Allmen, 1990).

CURRENT FUNDING FOR FAMILY SERVICES TO ETHNO-CULTURAL GROUPS

The cost to society of mental health and family problems is vastly underestimated. Mental illness affects people from all walks of life, causing them and their families considerable hardship. One out of every eight Canadians can expect to be hospitalized for a mental illness at least once during his or her lifetime; and over the next 25 years we can expect a doubling of mental disorders for the elderly and a 40% increase in chronic functional disorders (Building Community Support for People, 1988:3). When one combines major psychiatric disorders, organic dementias, substance abuse, domestic violence, emotional problems, and family dysfunction, the total costs represent a high proportion of government expenditures. The fragmentation of these issues between ministries diminishes their impact.

In 1987 a joint United Way/MCSS/Metro Community Services report on ethnocultural agencies pointed out that their "diversity in funding arrangements and [their] complexity almost defies rationalization" (UWGT, 1987). Funding patterns and program criteria change almost annually. The report continued that "most respondents say the lack of funding, particularly stable funding is a major problem for those persons trying to establish community support services" (p.10). Agencies which must fill out numerous application forms annually for these shifting requirements experience continual organizational instability. Moreover, many of these under-funded community-based agencies lack the sophistication for effective grantsmanship. Under the circumstances, it is impressive that many agencies have been successful in delivering family services.

Part of the difficulty in assigning responsibility for the area of family counselling is the confusion between provincial ministries with respect to their responsibilities and mandates. For example, individual and family counselling at a Community Mental Health Service, funded by the Ministry of Health (MOH), may be delivered by social workers of the same qualifications performing the same activities to the same clients as social workers at a Family Services Association funded by the Ministry of Community and Social Services (MCSS). The distinctions between mental health services and family counselling services are often arbitrary and depend solely on where a client goes for help. A client may be referred by a psychiatrist for individual counselling to either a MOH-funded outpatient clinic or an MCSS-funded Family Services Association, while continuing to receive medication by the psychiatrist. In the first instance, MOH

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pays 100% of the cost; in the second, the client pays fee for service, with limited government funding through purchase of service agreements for welfare recipients, and charitable contributions picking up most of the rest. In essence, the voluntary sector has been paying for the shift to deinstitutionalization. The basic problem is one of resources; there is no secure funding base for any family service organization, much less those which serve ethnocultural groups.

Only about 15% of Metro agencies serving immigrant are funded by MCSS for social service programming, yet over 75% of these agencies provide some form of family counselling

Recently, the Ontario Ministry of Citizenship has clarified and focused its funding mandate towards more clearly defined settlement services. As a result, informal family services (which were never officially eligible for support) will no longer be funded through this ministry. There has been no corresponding move by MCSS to take responsibility for these vital social supports. According to the data from the Ontario Coalition of Agencies Serving Immigrants (1990), only about 15% of Metro agencies serving immigrants are funded by MCSS for social service programming, yet over 75% of these agencies provide some form of family counselling.

Employment and Immigration Canada, the Secretary of State and the Ministry of Citizenship are the main funders of settlement agencies, but few of their funding programs provide stable funding sufficient to allow agencies to develop and maintain effective management systems. Without stable core funding, these agencies are forced to expend significant time in securing inadequate short term grants and are often unable to hire and retain qualified staff. Their major funders do not recognize mental health or family counselling as 'settlement' issues; nor do they generally deal with adjustment problems that emerge after about three years of living in Canada.

The distinctions between mental health services and family counselling services are often arbitrary

PROVINCIAL GOVERNMENT DIRECTIONS RE: ETHNOCULTURAL GROUPS

The Ontario Government, in its Multiculturalism Strategy (1987), pledged that it would "formulate a five-year plan for ensuring that programs operated or funded by the province respond to the needs of a multicultural society". The Government further contracted to "plan, design and deliver programs and services in a manner which accommodates all segments of a multicultural, multiracial society".

In 1988, the Minister of Health stated that "our government has made a commitment to ensure that health care services will be available and accessible to everyone in this province regardless of economic status, geographic location and ethnic origin" (Caplan,

p.18). She emphasized "the importance of considering multicultural issues in program planning and development.... There is perhaps no area of health care where culture and ethnic sensitivities are more important than in the care and treatment of people with psychiatric disabilities" (p.19).

The Corporate Plan of the Ministry of Community and Social Services, released in January 1990, stated that "the Government is committed to addressing the cultural and linguistic barriers facing new immigrants and to improving their access to mainstream services in ways that ensure the social service system accurately reflects Ontario's multicultural, multiracial society (p.7).... A co-ordinated system of flexible, accessible and culturally sensitive community support services [will be] provided for those with special needs (p.14).... The service system must develop alternative approaches to prevent family and individual problems ... [by] addressing the causes of social problems and building on the adaptive strengths of individuals, families and communities" (p.17). The Corporate Plan emphasizes that programs provided in the community should be "sensitive and responsive to local cultural traditions and values" (p.19).

Up until now, the Ontario government has stated no specific funding policies nor criteria regarding health and social services for ethnocultural groups

To date, the Ontario government has no stated funding policies nor criteria regarding health and social services for ethnocultural groups.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

One of the most urgent social service issues for the nineties is the lack of appropriate social support for the diverse ethnocultural families that make up Metro Toronto. United Way identified this as a concern in 1982. During the intervening years, the magnitude and significance of this gap has continued to grow.

The family service needs of immigrants and ethnocultural groups must be viewed in the context of the entire settlement and adaptation process, in which members of the immigrant family gradually become 'bicultural' (see Appendix A). Family functioning should be addressed at the very beginning of the immigration process, and services planned to respond to family needs as they go through the phases of adaptation. Even after full integration into Canadian life, family services should be delivered with cultural and racial sensitivity and appropriateness.

Family functioning should be addressed at the very beginning of the immigration process; even after full integration into Canadian life, family services should be delivered with cultural and racial sensitivity

Ontario, and Metro in particular, can be proud of its strong voluntary sector. Many ethnocultural communities point with justifiable pride to the network of services they have developed to meet the needs. Many of our community-wide agencies have a solid record of responding to changing demographic patterns over many years.

In the 1990s we must find ways to effectively channel this tradition and commitment in light of the incredible ethnocultural diversity of Metro and the increasing demands being placed on community support services. The challenge is all the greater because of the very limited programs of public funding for family support services. The shortfall between the cost of delivering services and the level of reimbursement by government has been well documented (SARC, 1988). Moreover, the current confusion regarding responsibility for planning, funding and delivering mental health services, specific 'special needs' services, family counselling and community-based preventative programs needs to be addressed.

An effective policy and funding strategy must:

- Embrace cultural and racial diversity and, at the same time, foster the ability of ethnocultural and racial groups to participate fully in community life.
- Recognize the important role of ethnocultural agencies, but also encourage all agencies to be responsive to ethnocultural and racial diversity.
- Provide adequate government funding for family services.
- Enhance the capacity of ethnocultural and local community-based agencies to support individuals and families.
- Develop and evaluate models of service delivery to ensure that, not only are appropriate family services accessible to new Canadians, but also that the services result in better lives for families and individuals.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Access to Family Services for Ethnocultural Groups

This paper has identified a major gap in the provision of family services to ethnocultural groups. To a large extent this is related to the fragmentation of services between different levels and Ministries of government. Although Long Term Care Reform attempts to rationalize and coordinate some human services between Ministries, the enormous area of mental health and family services remains largely unaddressed.

The overlap between mental health and social services, especially in family support, creates inefficiencies and confusion. It makes no sense, for example, that family counselling is free when delivered by a psychiatrist, but not when delivered by a social worker, even though the same service may cost government three times as much when delivered by a psychiatrist. The funding of family support must recognize appropriate professional qualifications for each function, and attempt to maximize service for dollars. Currently, the most underfunded services are often the most cost efficient, and community-based preventive approaches are disqualified by funding criteria despite growing evidence of the importance of prevention.

The Ministry of Health is in the process of developing Community Mental Health legislation to outline the essential functions and responsibilities of the health care system in this area. To some extent, health-related costs are protected by existing legislation and funding agreements from the federal and provincial governments. There is a need for parallel legislation regarding community services, which includes many of the family supports provided by social agencies. In fact, MCSS is presently working on "a new Community Services Act that will consolidate legislation for a number of community-based services now covered by separate acts, such as Elderly Persons' Centres and Homemakers and Nurses Services" (MCSS - PMSSR Report, 1990, p.193). It is essential that this Act be integrated with the Community Mental Health Act to minimize overlap and confusion. Without such a Community Services Act, and with the present cost-sharing system, family services will be at the mercy of municipal governments, which (according to one respondent) "sometimes think the town marching band is more important than the local woman's shelter". Municipalities must be responsible for ensuring certain essential services, including some form of support to families.

We recommend the following:

1. That a Community Services Act be introduced to define essential community and family supports to be provided in municipalities across Ontario, along with their respective funding responsibilities.
2. That key ministries (Community and Social Services; Health; Citizenship; and others, where appropriate) co-ordinate policy and funding roles related to family services, and redistribute funds to maximize effectiveness and accessibility to the families who need them.
3. That, in the meantime, existing programs be changed and expanded to meet current needs, while studying approaches and models that work.

We suggest implementing these recommendations in two phases, starting with programme changes. Work on the policy and legislative changes should begin as soon as possible, building on the findings of the evaluations built into the pilot programs.

Phase 1: Programme changes

1. MCSS, Metro and United Way should jointly fund a pilot program of alternative service delivery models (see Appendix C for a detailed description of the proposal). Evaluation of family service models to ethnocultural groups should be supported in order to better understand what kinds of approaches work best with diverse ethnocultural groups. Research should focus on productive and cost-effective models for family services linking mainstream organizations (such as substance abuse treatment centres) with ethnocultural agencies.
2. Interpreters should be available to meet the needs of various ethnocultural groups, along with training in cultural sensitivity for the service providers who use them.
3. All agencies should be expected and supported to develop multicultural/anti-racist policies and programs, including recruitment and training procedures. UWGT is currently planning the implementation of its Anti-racism Policy, which will begin to address this issue among its member agencies.
4. Community development should be supported for ethnocultural groups who have not yet established stable organizations.
5. Programs should be provided to assist agencies serving immigrants and ethnocultural groups with organizational development. UWGT could

deliver some of these services through its Management Assistance Program.

Phase 2: Policy changes

6. A comprehensive program for developing and funding family services should be introduced by the Provincial government, recognizing the respective contributions of local, ethnocultural and community-wide agencies.
7. Stable funding should be available for ethnocultural agencies so that they will have the capacity to provide effective family services. As the SARC Report, recommendation 143 states: "Multicultural organizations should be retained to provide information, advocacy, referral services, community education, consultation on specific cases, assessments and counselling".

Agencies which meet criteria for service provision and serve a population of demonstrated need should be eligible for funding for family counselling/mental health services. They should not be restricted solely because they serve a particular ethnocultural group.

8. The current policy co-ordination efforts of senior staff of the various levels of government (Metro Community Services; the Ontario Ministries of Citizenship, and Community and Social Services; the Federal Department of Secretary of State and the Immigration Settlement and Adaptation Program) with United Way should be supported and enhanced. The Ministry of Health should also be involved.

Appendix A

GLOSSARY

Acronyms

MCSS	-	Ministry of Community & Social Services
MOH	-	Ministry of Health
SARC	-	Social Assistance Review Committee, MCSS
UWGT	-	United Way of Greater Toronto

Bicultural

A 'bicultural' or 'integrated' Canadian has the tools to engage in the major functions and activities of community life, such as the ability to enter a vocation of his/her choice. Tools would include, for example, English or French literacy. Integration does not imply an acceptance of Western values and cultural assumptions regarding personal and family life. After three generations of settlement, one can assume that native-born Canadians are integrated in this sense (through public education, at least), without assuming that they have given up their families' cultural heritage.

Employment and Immigration Canada (1990) states, "For a newcomer to Canada, successful integration means the ability to contribute, free of barriers, to every dimension of Canadian life -- economic, social, cultural and political" (p.9).

Canada's official commitment to multiculturalism would suggest that services should be delivered in a variety of cultural and linguistic modalities to meet the needs of diverse groups in Canada, as a matter of cultural heritage and human rights. The issue of 'choice' in this context, for people who can benefit from 'mainstream services', is highly controversial. This paper takes a pragmatic view; at present, many first- and second-generation immigrants have no access to adequate family services. We must respond to their needs, regardless of debates about whether third- and fifth-generation Canadians should have guaranteed access to specialized culturally focused services.

Community-based Agencies

In this paper, 'community-based' is used to refer to agencies which are responsive to specific communities, which may be defined geographically (the Jane-Finch neighbourhood) or ethnoculturally (the Jamaican-Canadian Association). In either case, agencies have a clear 'local flavour' in that they are attempting to serve a particular client group. Usually they are multi-service agencies.

Ethnocultural Agencies

These agencies are devoted to serving one or more defined ethnocultural group(s). When they serve clients of only one ethnicity (for example, the Vietnamese Association), they may be referred to as ethnospecific agencies.

Mainstream Agencies

'Mainstream' is a rather unclear term which is widely used to mean many different kinds of agencies. In this paper, it refers to agencies which are geographically based and do not have a mandate to serve any particular ethnocultural group. Mainstream agencies which are mandated to serve the entire Metro Toronto area are occasionally referred to as 'community-wide' agencies. Please note that, under these definitions, a small local mainstream agency can also be a community-based agency.

Family Services

The Multicultural Coalition for Access to Family Services defines family services as follows:

1. Individual, marital, family, group counselling and/or therapy provided and supervised by appropriately trained people who are linguistically competent, culturally sensitive and knowledgeable.
2. Outreach and public education on family life and social issues.
3. Research, consultation, staff/volunteer training and development.

The Metro Social Planning Council defines family services as follows:

"Family services is a mix of services whose goal is to support and strengthen individuals and their families; it also includes the case management (client related) functions required to support the provision of services.... [The elements of case management functions (client related) include:] reception, intake, eligibility assessment, documentation, information and referral, needs assessment, case planning, contracting, advocacy, monitoring, case recording, [and] case evaluation.

"Elements of family services in general include services that are provided to persons in need, e.g., escort, information and referral, homemaking services, counselling, child care, senior services, day care.... Excluded are the range of other agency functions such as: research; planning; resource development; organization; control; monitoring; and evaluation" (Doyle, 1989).

Mental Health Services

The essential functions of a mental health system cover a very wide range of services, according to a recent report by the Ministry of Health (Building Community Support for People: A Plan for Mental Health in Ontario:1988). There is a great deal of overlap between the following functions described by this report, and family services as defined above:

- . Identification and diagnosis
- . Treatment and crisis support
- . Consultation from various health and social service disciplines
- . Co-ordination between different services
- . Residential support
- . Case co-ordination and case management
- . Social support
- . Vocational support
- . Self-help/peer support
- . Family support
- . Advocacy.

Appendix B

INTERVIEWS AND MEETINGS WITH GROUPS

A. List of Key Informants

1. Eva Allmen Ministry of Community and Social Services, Family Support Branch
2. Dan Andrae Ontario Association of Professional Social Workers, Re: Proposed Social Work Legislation
3. Caryl Arundel Metro Community Services Department, Policy and Planning Division
4. Al Burrows Ministry of Health, Re: Health Profession Legislation
5. Henry Chong Secretary of State Department
6. Brian Davidson Community Mental Health, Ministry of Health
7. Hinda Goldberg Multicultural Coalition for Access to Family Services
8. Irene Ilchyshyn Metro Community Services Department
9. Clive Joakim Citizenship Development Branch, Ministry of Citizenship
10. Rose Lee Hong Fook Mental Health Centre
11. Joe Manion Metro Community Services Department, Policy and Planning Division
12. Andrea Maurice Ministry of Citizenship
13. Leslie Morris Community Resources Consultants of Toronto
14. Nancy Newton Ministry of Citizenship
15. Susan Pigott Family Services Association
16. Rosemary Popham United Ways of Ontario, Government Relations Program
17. Wendy Quirion Immigrant Settlement and Adaptation Program (ISAP), of the Employment and Immigration Canada
18. Ted Richmond Ontario Council of Agencies Serving Immigrants (OCASI)
19. Howard Sinclair-Jones Ontario Council of Agencies Serving Immigrants (OCASI)
20. Staff and Associates United Way of Greater Toronto, Allocations and Community Relations Department

B. List of Groups

1. Family Services to Ethnocultural Communities: Working Group
2. Metro Working Group for Multicultural Services

Appendix C

JOINT FUNDING PROPOSAL FOR FAMILY SERVICES

The joint funding model of the Community/Neighbourhood Social Services Program (CNSSP) has been tremendously successful in supporting locally based multi-service agencies in delivering a wide range of programs to their communities. The United Way proposes that a similar collaborative approach be used to address the severe gaps in family service to ethnocultural groups. At the same time, we must ensure that a limited funding stream will not merely create more frustration and expectations without solving the long-term problems of access.

Specifically, we support the recommendation of the Multicultural Coalition For Access to Family Services for All: that a three-year transitional project jointly funded by United Way, Metro Community Services and the Ministry of Community and Social Services be established in consultation with community groups to fund and evaluate four different models of service delivery. We propose that a minimum budget of \$1 million a year is necessary in order to adequately test these models:

1. Direct support to ethnocultural agencies which have demonstrated competence in the delivery of family services or the potential to deliver such services.
2. Funds to ethnocultural agencies to purchase required services from established family services agencies, such as clinical supervision, case consultation, staff training and programme consultation.
3. Funds to established family services agencies to purchase consultative services (including outreach programmes and cross-cultural training) from ethnocultural agencies.
4. Funds to be jointly administered by ethnocultural and established family services agencies, in order to place trained clinical staff in ethnocultural agencies. Program and staff accountability would be shared.

Approximately ten projects should be funded, with individual budgets between \$50,000 to \$150,000 depending on the scope of the project and the size of the community it will serve. (The average salary of a social worker in a UWGT member agency is \$32,000). Part of the grant should go to administration. Each grant should be made for a three-year term.

There should be a combination of large and small agencies (including both ethnocultural and mainstream), and at least one example of each model of service delivery. The exact process of setting criteria and ranking proposals should be developed in consultation with the Multicultural Coalition and key community representatives.

The funding project should include a staff position, with responsibilities to include program development and consultation, evaluation, and a review with recommendations at the end of the three years. During this three year period, a comprehensive program for developing and funding family support services should be developed, recognizing the respective contributions of local, ethnospecific and community-wide agencies.

The breakdown of the costs, consistent with the respective responsibilities of MCSS, Metro and United Way for family services, would be identical to the funding ratio for Home Support agencies. For a project of \$1 million, the Provincial Government would contribute \$700,000, Metro would contribute \$200,000 and United Way \$100,000 per year.

Appendix D

**FAMILY SERVICES FOR ALL: STUDY OF FAMILY SERVICES FOR
ETHNOCULTURAL AND RACIAL COMMUNITIES IN METRO TORONTO**

by The Multicultural Coalition For Access to Family Services

RECOMMENDATIONS

Criteria for Family Services

We recommend that the criteria for the definition and delivery of family services include key factors, such as immigration and refugee status, language ability, and cultural and racial differences, that affect the lives of members of ethnocultural and racial communities.

Role of Ethnocultural and Racial Community Agencies

We recommend that funders recognize the vital role of ethnocultural and racial community agencies in the identification of needs and in the provision of family services to their own communities.

Service Delivery Models

We recommend that:

- A three-year pilot project jointly funded by United Way, Metro Community Services and the Ontario Ministry of Community and Social Services be established in consultation with the Multicultural Coalition for Access to Family Services and other family services organizations to fund the following service delivery models:
 1. Provide direct and continuing support to ethnocultural and racial community agencies which have demonstrated competence in the delivery of family services or the potential to deliver such services.
 2. Support ethnocultural and racial community agencies that may purchase required services from established family services agencies. Such services may include supervision, case consultation, staff training and programme consultation.
 3. Provide funds to established family services agencies to purchase consultative services from ethnocultural and racial community agencies. Such consultative services may include developing outreach programmes and cross-cultural training.
 4. Support a partnership between ethnocultural and racial community agencies and established family services agencies. Funding should go to both established family services agencies for staff and to ethnocultural and racial community agencies for administrative support and rent. Programme and staff accountability should be shared.

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5. Support a co-location arrangement in which more than one established family services agency will place staff in an ethnocultural and racial community agency to provide family services.

(This pilot project should have an evaluation and research component and include community consultation as an integral part of the process).

- There should be flexibility in new family services provided to ensure that linguistically appropriate, culturally and racially sensitive family services are available.

Funding Policy

We recommend that:

- Funders review their funding criteria to ensure that ethnocultural and racial community agencies have equal and equitable access to stable funds directed to family services and purchase of service agreements.
- That United Way, Metro Community Services and the Ontario Ministry of Community and Social Services review current funding programmes and priorities and develop clear funding policies regarding the provision of linguistically appropriate, culturally and racially sensitive family services by appropriately trained staff.
- Information on programmes to fund family services be made available to all agencies.
- Metro Community Services and the Ontario Ministry of Community and Social Services ensure that their shared cost counselling programmes be made accessible to ethnocultural and racial community agencies.
- Funding to provide family services to the ethnocultural and racial communities not be marginalized in a special funding programme, but become part of the system.
- The wife assault initiative be expanded, and more emphasis be given to the needs of immigrant women and women of non-dominant cultures.

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